

Investigating the effects of the new technology revolution In the third millennium

Pourya Zarshenas

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University
pouryazarshenas@yahoo.com

Abstract

The age of knowledge is in fact the result of the gradual accumulation of advances in the age of automation, which began two hundred and fifty years ago at the same time as the emergence of the British textile industry. The thousands of machines and tools that gradually emerged after the First Industrial Revolution changed the nature of work. In fact, the lower steps in the skill ladder were occupied by all kinds of machines, and on the other hand, new and higher steps were added to the skill ladder.

Perhaps the most important feature of the knowledge age is the decentralization of power. Today, knowledge does not only increase wealth or power, but knowledge itself is wealth and power. The greater our ability to acquire knowledge, the better we can determine our individual destiny.

Today is the turn of the digital revolution and the technology revolution, including information and communication technology. These technologies provide the tools for instant transmission of text, audio and video data, anywhere in the world. They also allow easy storage of data, allowing data to be recovered at any time. Information technology is both a tool and a goal. Clearly, information technology is the driving force behind the civilization of the 21st century, in a way that brutally integrates its methods into all areas of economic life and, equally, into our personal lives. The capabilities of foresight and the characteristics of knowledge and the methods used in it have reached a stage that has become a significant and useful tool in converting knowledge and information into practical programs and applications. Futurism has gone through various stages in its evolution from purely technical predictions to its development in the sense of futurism. Today, foresight, especially in the field of information and communication science and technology, has become an important tool for decision-making, policy-making and strategic planning due to the development and evolution of its concepts and methods.

Keywords: New Technology Revolution, Information Technology, Third Millennium